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The Role of Interactive Technologies in Training Future Teachers of Russian Literature

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Abstract

A modern school places heavy demands on the personality and professional qualities of a modern teacher of literature. First of all, the teacher must know his subject, be ready for constant self-education, be ready to acquire new knowledge and skills in his subject, to know the main stages of the development of Russian literature, to conduct a comparative analysis of the phenomena of Russian literature with the main directions of the development of literature of the peoples of Russia and the world literature as a whole. The aim of our study is to justify theoretically and devise methodologically a system of classroom studies with the use of interactive and digital technologies at university (Kazan Federal University). This allows us to develop professional habits and practical skills of future school teachers of Russian literature for the effective teaching of modern Russian literature at school. In our study use has been made of the following methods: theoretical (the study of literary, psychological and pedagogical research), as well as empirical (pedagogical experiment (ascertaining, transforming and control), generalization of our own pedagogical experience of work at school and University, observation, conversation and interviewing of 100 students, university and school teachers of the city of Kazan, etc.).

In the course of research the following results were obtained: methodic guidelines for the use of interactive and digital technologies in the classroom studies of historical, literary and pedagogical disciplines were theoretically devised and implemented into the practice of professional training of teachers of Russian literature at the University.

Let us consider different forms of classroom work on the example of studying the discipline "The ways of integrating the works of modern Russian literature into the practice of school teaching" for the students doing their master's course in "Philological education" at Kazan Federal University. In this article, the proposed method is demonstrated by the example of practical training on the work of modern Russian writer Valentin Rasputin.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that methodological recommendations and guidelines were proposed, theoretically justified and tested during our experimental work, in order to introduce interactive and digital technologies in the process of training future teachers of Russian literature. It is determined that the systematic use of interactive methods in the University practice of teaching historical, literary and pedagogical disciplines can effectively develop professional habits and skills of future school teachers of literature and also allows them to form critical thinking, creates a positive motivation in the implementation of their professional activities, develops communication skills and meta-subject skills that are necessary for the systematic use of interactive and digital technologies in their own teaching activities.

The results of the study can be used in preparation of programs and textbooks on the methodology of teaching literature at school and university, and the proposed system of practical training can be implemented in the practice of teaching modern literature at schools and universities.

Keywords: methods of teaching literature, interactive learning technologies, modern Russian literature, methods, techniques, modern literature, Valentin Rasputin

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Introduction

A modern teacher of literature should know both traditional methods and techniques of teaching literature, and the latest technologies of teaching. Therefore, it is necessary to revise the system of training of future teachers of Russian literature at universities. In the formation of personal and professional qualities of future teachers of literature a significant role is played by methods, techniques and forms of teaching historical and literary courses at university. These problems are well developed in relation to school methods of teaching literature, but in the university practice of teaching historical and literary disciplines there is a predominance of traditional forms (lectures, practical classes and seminars) and knowledge control (tests, examinations in the form of questions and answers), which offer primarily reproductive methods of learning. In the first decades of the XXI century there are significant changes in the modern methods of teaching Humanities, including literature, due to the principles of "the openness of education", the implementation of the principle of "the access to education for everybody", the introduction of ICT and digital technologies, the development of distance learning, developed in the works of Polat & Buharkina (2010), Buharkina (2017), Selevko, (2005a, 2005b, 1998). In the "Federal state standard of secondary (complete) general education", approved in 2012, amongst the key requirements to employees of educational institutions, are called the ability to "carry out an independent search and analysis of information using modern information retrieval technologies; to develop programs of training courses, methodological and didactic materials, to choose textbooks and teaching-methodical literature, to recommend students additional sources of information, including Internet resources" [FSES, 2012, p. 16].

Nowadays, however, there is a lack of scientific research on modern methods of teaching literature at the university. Buranok (1997) and Katorova (2004) to a greater extent developed the content of teaching Russian literature at university, which met the needs of the practice of teaching literature in the 1990s. In this regard, we have studied the works on the methods of teaching literature at school and also the related humanitarian disciplines at the university, which outline methodological approaches to solving modern problems of university methods of teaching humanitarian disciplines (Ibragimov, Galimullina, & Shemshurenko, 2017; Mukhametshina & Galimullina, 2014; Erofeeva & Nurullina, 2017; Fazliakhmetov

& Yusupova, 2016; Kharisov & Kharisova, 2016; Pashkurov et al., 2017). In modern pedagogical and methodical investigations the issues of personal development of students in their subject matter and practical activities are actively developed, as well as the problem of introduction of active and integrative forms and methods of education based on activity and dialogue forms of knowledge. In this connection, the choice of the topic of our research and its relevance are conditioned by the following reasons: 1) the need to develop theoretically grounded methodological recommendations on the introduction of the works of modern Russian literature into the school curriculum on the basis of contextual and comparative study of the works included in the existing school curricula in literature and proposed by the authors of the given study for the introduction into the circle of reading of modern teenagers; 2) the search for methods and techniques to improve the quality of university training of future school teachers of literature.

In the 1990s-2000s information technologies and Internet resources were actively introduced into the school methods of teaching literature (Mukhametshina & Galimullina, 2014). In addition, various types of lessons were developed that made it possible to implement the activity approach in the most efficient way, such as integrated lessons, lessons-debates, a literary salon, a literary and theatrical marathon, and a lesson-literary workshop. Therefore, students, future teachers of literature should also master methods and technologies to activate learning, not only theoretically, but also when they master historical, literary and psychological-pedagogical disciplines and disciplines on their choice should be taught using these technologies, which will allow students to gain experience of pedagogical interaction.

In connection with the practical absence of special scientific and methodological research on the issues under consideration, in relation to the university course of teaching literature, we have developed guidelines for conducting classes in modern Russian literature on the example of the study of the novel "Money for Maria" by Valentin Rasputin. We propose the discussion forms of class work (work in pairs, in small groups, analysis of situations of moral choice, etc.), game and training technologies of teaching literature to be used more actively.

Materials and research methods

Questioning, interviewing of 100 university teachers and students, as well as the analysis of more than 25 years of teaching experience at university showed that the leading role in the practice of teaching modern Russian literature is given to the traditional forms of organization of the activities of teachers and students: lectures, workshops, seminars, independent work of students and teaching practice. We propose to include elements of the role-play (staging the episodes of literary works), mini-conferences, the use of case-technology, as well as the method of "brainstorming" which will allow to make the discussion of the works of modern Russian literature more dynamic.

The basis of our research was formed by historical and genetic, historical and functional, comparative and typological approaches to consider the works of modern Russian literature in the context of development of the world and Russian literary process at the synchronic and diachronic levels.

Final results of lectures, workshops and seminars can be received by the teacher through organizing oral discussions, exchange of opinions with the whole class (20-30 students) and in small groups (4-6 students), through graphic images (making tables, laughter, clusters on the topics: "Literary genres, schools, currents of Russian literature at the end of the XX - the beginning of the XXI centuries", "Postmodernism in Russian literature at the end of the XX - the beginning of the XXI centuries" or "Realism in Russian literature at the end of the XX - the beginning of the XXI centuries", etc.), or in the form of the "unfinished sentence". One of the methods of reflection on the studied material can be a

thematic crossword puzzle created by students on the basis of the results of their study of the monographic theme ("Creativity of Valentin Rasputin", "Life and works of Ludmila Ulitskaya", "Creative research of Ludmila Petrushevskaya", etc.), as well as making a synquain on the theme of the lesson. For example, according to the novel "Money for Maria" students invented such a synquain:

Maria
 Kind, selfless
 Helps, trusts, suffers
 "You have to be human to live with people"
 The victim of circumstances.

Discussion of the synquains composed by students may be the beginning or the end of the work with Rasputin's story (you can offer students to make synquains on the images of Kuzma (Maria's husband), Alexei's brother, etc.).

At practical lessons the work can be organized both in the academic group of 20-30 students, and in small groups (from 4 to 6 students), in pairs, combined with presentations of the results of various types of independent, original work (reports on the problem of the lesson, reports on the monograph, scientific article, writing an article or a report, essay, course work, final qualification work, master's thesis). The study of various aspects of literary criticism of the modern Russian literature, as well as the solution of problems associated with the integration of the modern Russian literature in the school course of literature, which is relevant both for modern literary criticism and methods, causes research interest among students. Plans and working programs of elective and optional courses, school plans for lessons devoted to the study of the creativity of modern Russian writers are worked out by students independently and then presented in public.

Thus, for example, Anastasia Vinogradova, a 2-year graduate student offered a program of an elective course to be studied in the 10-11 grades on the theme "Genre and typological peculiarities of the works in prose at the postmodern stage of development of literature of the XXI century (1989-2010s)", which contained the following authors and their works: T. Tolstaya "Kys" ("Yorik"), B. Akunin "Adventures of Erast Fandorin" ("Azazel", "The Diamond Chariot"), V. Pelevin "Chapaev and the Void", Z. Prilepin "The Sin", D. Yemets "In the Claws of the Stone Age", L. Ulitskaya "Medea and her children", "The Green Tent", "The Kukotsky's Casus", "Sonia", L. Petrushevskaya "A Glass of Water", "A Country", "Time of Night", E. Grishkovets "Winter", "How I Ate the Dog", D. Rubina "Do Not Leave Me Alone", M. Petrosyan "The House In Which ...", F. Iskander "The Uninvited Guest", G. Sadulayev "I am a Chechen", D. Granin "My Lieutenant", E. Voyskunsky "Rumyantsevsky Square", R. Sechin "The Flood Zone", D. Bykov "Happiness", "Spelling, the Opera in Three Acts", "Animals and Beasts", P. Basinsky "Russian Romance, or Life and Adventures of John Polovinkin". And the graduate student of the master's course Leysan Sharafutdinova offered her own version of the elective course "The Modern Literature", focusing on the works that either reveal philosophical and moral problems of our time or are united thematically. Her elective course allows us to trace the development of prose in recent decades, to consider the urban prose through understanding the fate of a man in the modern world, as well as to compare contemporary works that reveal the problem of "a man at war" with the previous literature on the subject. The following authors and works for reading and discussion at the elective course are offered by L. Sharafutdinova: V.G. Rasputin "Money for Maria", "Unexpectedly Unexpected", V. Astafiev "Ludochka", "The Last Bow", "Cursed and Killed", "Shepherd and Shepherdess", E. Nosov "Apple Saved", O. Ermakov "The Last Story of War", A. Prokhanov "Kandagarskaya Zastava", V. Makanin "Caucasian Prisoner", "Laz",

"Underground", T. Tolstaya "Kys", A.Varlamov "The Mountain", "Baikal", L. Petrushevskaya "One`s own Circle", " The Waterloo Bridge", "As an Angel", "The Country", "Glitch", Sasha Sokolov "School for Fools", L.Ulitskaya "The Pearl-Barley Soup", "The Art of Living", "The Daughter of Bukhara", "And Died at One and the Same Day", E.L.Schwartz "The Dragon", "The Shadow", A.Ivanov "A Geographer Swapped a Globe for Drink", V.Tokareva "A Long Day", "The Happy End", A.Kim "Under the Shade of Nut Trees", L.N.Razumovskaya "Dear Elena Sergeevna", "French Passions at a Dacha near Moscow", A.A.Zvyagintsev "Natural Selection", Yuri Mamleev "A Morning", "A Fiancé", Mikhail Petrosyan "House in which...", Marcus Zuzak "A Book Thief", David Grossman "Who To Run With", "The Chicken Broth, 101 Inspirational Stories", Kaverin "Two Captains", V. Belov "Carpenter`s Stories", T. Vossoevich "A Military Diary and Siege Letters. June 22, 1941 - June 1, 1945", A. Azolsky "Saboteur", M. Tarkavsky "A Hike", E. Vodolazkin "Solovyov and Larionov", "Lavr", "Aviator", D. Sugralinov "Bricks", V. Maximov "A Living Soul", K. Shishkin "Liberation-2", A. Marinina "A Bitter Quest". When discussing the programs of elective courses students should demonstrate their well-formed skills of critical thinking, clearly articulate the selection criteria, at the lesson there is a discussion on what criteria it is possible to select works of art for the student audience, what criteria should the work of art correspond to: the age-related psycho-physiological ability of schoolchildren to perceive , high moral and ethical standards, be a highly artistic work, etc.

The use of case technology as a kind of the research method is one of the most effective techniques when studying the story "Money for Maria" by Valentin Rasputin. The case method usually consists of several stages: 1) introduction to the case; 2) situation analysis; 3) presentation; 4) general discussion; 5) summary.

A strategic case study involves the development of skills to analyze the environment under uncertainty and solve complex problems with hidden determinants, so we suggest students to answer the following questions: What will happen to Maria? Will they raise the necessary money? Will her brother help her?

Each group of students was given a task on the cards with the description of the case-situation from V.G.Rasputin`s story "Money for Maria" with the following questions: 1) What problems are raised in this work? Formulate and write down on the sheet of paper; 2) What ways of solving a problem or problems does the author suggest? 3) Have you encountered similar problems in the works of Russian classical literature? 4) Which of the classics raised this problem and how it was solved? 5) What solution do you propose? 6) Was it possible to act differently and what were the consequences?

The cards offer auxiliary resources: Leo Tolstoy "War and Peace" (The episode "The Lost 40 thousand (Nikolai and Count Rostov)", Mikhail Saltykov-Shchedrin "The Golovlevs" (Porfiry Petrovich and his son), Nikolai Gogol "The Dead Souls" (Plyushkin and his son), F.M.Dostoevsky "The Crime and the Punishment" (Marmeladov's Death), etc. The task of the case is to formulate the supposed solution of the problem from the novel "Money for Maria" by V.G.Rasputin and to confirm the solution of the problem's with examples: 1) The problem raised in the story; 2) Analysis of the situation; 3) The way out of the situation (what does the author suggest?); 4) Which solution did you take? 5) Was it possible to act differently? What were the consequences? 6) Is the problem relevant and why?

Rasputin's story ends with the words: " And he has come – pray, Maria! “, pronounced by Alexey, Maria`s brother at the moment when her husband Kuzma is ringing the bell of her brother`s door. The open ending of the story helps to sharpen the situation, makes students read the story attentively and match the situation with classical works where the heroes needed money and were asking their family for help.

This case corresponds to the main requirement for a training case: the proposed situation should reflect the real story, and it should be distinguished by problematical character and dramatism.

At the final stage of the lesson the teacher sums up the content of the case, and confirms the conclusions made by students. He evaluates the most successful organization of students' work in small groups: the time spent on the task, the activity of each participant of the small group, the quality of the response to the case. So the case method allows students to realize their creative abilities, forms the skills of collective problem solving in small groups, develops speech and communication skills, and creates the situation of success.

Result

Formation of professional qualities of the future teacher of Russian language and literature in the context of classical university (Kazan Federal University) is effective when keeping to general didactic principles, as well as specific methods and techniques which depend upon the fact that literature is one of the arts. The work on modern Russian literature can be continued when studying the discipline "Methods of teaching literature", the disciplines on choice "Integration of the works of modern Russian literature in the practice of teaching literature at school" and during pedagogical practice. Various types of activities (the analysis of alternative school programs in Russian literature, textbooks, making synopsis of the lesson and presentations) provide an opportunity even for the first-year students to begin to apply knowledge gained in historical and literary disciplines in their practical activity. The discipline in the methods of teaching literature and pedagogical practice at schools enable students (bachelors, masters) to consolidate their historical, literary and theoretical knowledge. Students-probationers, working in 9-11 grades, test their development in methods (abstracts of lessons, extracurricular activities, excursions, working programs of elective and optional courses, etc.) during their school practice. The continuity between historical, literary and methodical disciplines at university creates conditions for successful formation of students' deep understanding of the modern Russian literature and also for the formation of sustainable skills in mastering methods and interactive technologies of teaching at school.

In the course of the given study and during the training experiment at lectures and practical classes with students, we came to the following conclusions.

The formation of professional qualities of future teachers of Russian language and literature is carried out in the study of historical and literary disciplines, as well as in the formation of metasubject skills during their independent research activities, during their independent and comprehensive analysis of the literary text.

Thus, for the correct solution of the case on the story "Money for Maria" by V. G. Rasputin, students have to carry out a meticulous work with the artistic embodiment of images, with figurative and expressive means of the language of the story (proverbs and sayings), altered proverbs, phraseological units and stable phrases), with natural images (wind, snow), which help to deepen and sharpen the psychology of the story, and become symbolic (for example, the action of the story spreads to the continuous accompaniment of the wind ("And, nevertheless, I am anxious. One comes after another: the wind, the story with the ticket and now this dream", with the elements of the plot and the composition of the work (a dream, a landscape, etc.). Characteristics of the characters of the story are considered through their attitude to money and then students draw their own conclusions.

Lexical work can be based on the observation and analysis of the word "silence". In relation to the room, the house it is quiet. The psychological state of the characters is reflected in the special atmosphere

of the house: "the hut is large, new, but it is so quiet, that it has an unlive- in look" (Rasputin, 1994, p. 89). The quiet is as tense, as the silence of Kuzma and Maria. Maria "didn't cry anymore. She was silent. If you ask her about something, she will answer with two or three words, and again she is silent (Rasputin, 1994, p. 88). The sad, tragic silence of Maria is more eloquent than words and tears – it is her silence that makes the reader feel the inner sufferings of the heroine, and the hopelessness of the situation. Klava, her friend, sympathizes with Maria: "she silently made Maria sit on the bed, sat down next to her and hugged her, pressed herself close to her, and began wailing with strong and clean, as on the choruses, voice" (Rasputin, 1994, p. 88).

The silence of Kuzma is different: "he comes in and keeps silent. The very thing that he had come was to tell everything to the people. But they are also silent, and this silence, in turn, also tells him more than any other words" (Rasputin, 1994, p. 89).

Lexical work with contextual antonyms opens up a deep understanding of the author's intention. "Someone will keep mum and someone will understand his position" (Rasputin, 1994, p. 89). Thus, the silence of the villagers means a refusal to help and their indifference to the misfortune of others.

After a detailed study of the motif of silence, eighth-graders come to the conclusion: the silence of Maria is a boundless grief, despair; the silence of Kuzma is a request for help, plea; the silence of the villagers means their indifference.

Discussion

The specifics of teaching literature at university is considered in the works of scientists-methodists (Buranok, 1997; Katorova, 2004), theoretical foundations of higher professional education are described in the works of Andreev (2005), Bondarevskaya (2010), Zagvjazinskiy et al. (2013), Slastenin (2010). In modern studies a great attention is given to problems of pedagogical design and modeling (Bespalenko, 2001), specificity of the use of information technologies in higher education institutions (M.Yu.Bukharkina, E.S.Polat). The works of Bizyaeva (2007) reveal various aspects of training of the future teacher, including the conditions of multicultural environment (Pashkurov et al., 2017; Salekhova, 2006). Issues on formation of professional knowledge and skills among students – future teachers are actively developed in the works of Bespalenko (2001). Meanwhile, observations on the organization of modern literary education of university students, oral surveys, surveys of teachers and students show that students are poorly guided in the modern literary process of Russia, actually they have no cognitive interest in modern Russian literature, they do not know the technologies of "critical thinking", which would allow them to objectively assess the artistic level of contemporary works and select works of modern literature in order to introduce them into their own circle of reading from the standpoint of high moral and ethical standards and age-appropriate psycho-physiological capabilities of perception. Insufficient development of conceptual bases of this problem in science and practice of university methodology of literature teaching determined the problems of our research.

Conclusion

In the course of the conducted research it was established that the systematic application of interactive methods in the university practice of teaching historical , literary and pedagogical disciplines allows the professional skills and habits of future school teachers of Russian literature to be formed effectively and assumes the fulfillment of the following conditions:

1. Multilevel, contextual and cultural approaches to the study of modern Russian literature;

2. Future teachers of literature should possess well-formed skills of "a qualified reader", which include systematic reading and analysis of the new works of art, reading "thick" literary-critical journals, awareness of the results of literary competitions ("A Poet", "A Big Book", etc.) and possession of skills of critical evaluation and selection of modern Russian literature in order to include schoolchildren into the process of literary education.

3. Systematic work on the formation and development of students' skills in application of modern educational technologies in the field of teaching reading, analysis and interpretation of the works of art, as well as the development of oral and written speech during the school practice in teaching literature.

4. Activity oriented content and organization of teaching of modern Russian literature to students of philological and pedagogical departments of universities, while maintaining the leading function of traditional forms of organization of the cognitive process (lectures, practical classes, pedagogical practice) with interactive forms of learning, educational activities within the framework of integrative disciplines of choice, contributing to the creation of positive motivation.

Recommendations

Professional qualities of future teachers of Russian literature are formed effectively by following general didactic principles, and also special methods and techniques resulting from the specificity of teaching literature as a kind of art (giving integrative lessons together with such disciplines as: "World art culture", "Russian art culture", etc.): a lecture-discussion, a lecture-conversation, a problem solving (case-technology), work in small groups, synquain, role-playing games (dramatization), mini-conferences, method of "brainstorming" multimedia-presentations, excursions by correspondence, etc.).

The formation of a harmonious personality of the future teacher of Russian literature will be facilitated by mastering such subject competences at university as: theoretical and literary concepts, analysis of the literary work, as well as the formation of professional competencies of the teacher of literature: mastering both traditional methods and techniques of teaching literature, and interactive learning technologies.

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